

PRO-SIS

Sviluppo e disseminazione di algoritmi per il progetto delle innovative strategie di protezione sismica "CONSTRAIN" e applicazione pilota su edifici esistenti in muratura

Razvoj in diseminacija postopkov za projektiranje inovativnega načina potresnega utrjevanja obstoječih zidanih stavb "CONSTRAIN"

Report 3.2
Risultati delle raccolte documentali tecniche sugli edifici pilota

Poročilo 3.2
Tehnična dokumentacija izbranih pilotnih stavb

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PRO-SIS

Development and dissemination of procedures for designing an innovative way seismic strengthening of existing masonry buildings "CONSTRAIN"

Report 3.2 Results of the technical documentation collections on the pilot buildings

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Report 3.2

Results of the technical documentation collected on the pilot buildings

Summary

1	Introduction	2
2	The building of ATER in Udine	3
2.1	Description of the structure (as-is status).....	3
2.2	Inspection of building structure and material testing	3
2.3	Description of any potential cracking and/or degradation scenario	25
2.4	Technical drawings	25
3	The building of ZVKDS in Ljubljana	26
3.1	Description of the structure (as-is status).....	26
3.2	Inspection of building structure and material testing	27
3.3	Description of any potential cracking and/or degradation scenario	33
3.4	Technical drawings	33
	Acknowledgments	34
	References.....	34

ANNEXES

A) Structural drawings of the building of ATER Udine – as is status

B) Structural drawings of the building of ZVKDS in Ljubljana – as is status

1 Introduction

The report collects the results of Activity 3.2 of the “PRO-SIS” project, titled “Collection of technical documentation regarding the construction characteristics of the selected buildings and the execution of in-situ tests”.

Within the CONSTRAIN project (INTERREG V-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2014-2020 - <https://2014-2020.ita-slo.eu/it/constrain>), strategies to reduce the seismic vulnerability of existing masonry were developed and tested in an extended experimental campaign. The developed strengthening method is based on the use of mortar coatings reinforced by fiber-based composite materials. The main advantage of the developed system is that it can be applied only on one side of the wall, which makes it much more convenient for residents and businesses. Due to construction works only on the outside of the building, people and their belongings don't have to be relocated, and business activity doesn't have to be interrupted. Furthermore, valuable artistic decorations can be preserved on the inside (or outside, when the inside side application is preferred). The developed strengthening method stands out because of its proven effectiveness by tests on structural components and on full scale pilot building.

The aim of the “PRO-SIS” project (INTERREG VI-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2021-2027 - <https://www.ita-slo.eu/it/pro-sis>) is to develop the necessary methods for the design and application of these strategies. For this purpose, the design procedures have been developed based on analytical and numerical analyses calibrated on the experimental results of “CONSTRAIN”. The results provide the designers with robust strategies for the design of the proposed systems, and instructions for design in commonly used commercial programs for design of structures.

In REPORT 3.1 [1], two selected case-study buildings are presented with related existing documentation and original drawings.

In this REPORT 3.2, all the technical information gathered from the analysis of historical documentation, inspections, surveys, in-situ tests are collected and discussed. The report has to main sections: one concerning the building of ATER Udine, and the other the building of ZVKDS in Ljubljana.

2 The building of ATER in Udine

2.1 Description of the structure (as-is status)

The building has a rectangular geometry of approximately 9 x 34 m². It has three storeys for residential use (floor height 3.20 m) and a semi-basement where the cellars are located. It has two stairwells, each serving two apartments per floor, for a total of six apartments per stairwell.

2.2 Inspection of building structure and material testing

Aim of the experimental tests is to obtain an LC2 level of knowledge for the assessment of the structural safety of the building, which corresponds to a confidence factor value of $CF = 1.20$. This level is achieved when the information gathered (visual surveys, experimental tests and interpretation of results) provides adequate knowledge of the geometry of the structure, the construction details and the mechanical characteristics of the materials, in particular:

- Geometry: the geometry of the structure is obtained from an accurate survey of the entire building in all its parts;
- Construction details: the construction details are obtained from an extensive in-situ verification of the connections between the walls and from a careful analysis of the masonry texture;
- Material properties: information on the mechanical characteristics of the materials is obtained from extensive in-situ tests. The number of tests was determined taking into account the homogeneity characteristics of the various types of structures.

Based on the level of knowledge chosen for the building (LC2) and taking into account the provisions of current legislation (National Standard Code NTC 2018, Circular no. 7, 2019), the following types of experimental investigations were first planned and then carried out.

For masonry elements:

- Characterisation of masonry texture;
- Endoscopic investigations;
- Penetrometric tests on mortar;
- Sonic tests;
- Single and double flat jack tests;
- Shove tests.

For reinforced concrete elements:

- Reinforcement surveys with pacometer;
- Pull-out tests;
- Sclerometric and ultrasonic surveys;
- Testing of floor slabs and joists.

2.2.1 Characterisation of masonry texture of the walls and endoscopic investigations

Localised removal of plaster and video endoscopic investigations have allowed to characterise the masonry texture and thickness of the load-bearing walls. The vertical structural elements are made of clay solid brick masonry, with two and three heads thick. These structural elements form the entire perimeter of the building, as well as the internal walls both in longitudinal and transversal directions. The total thickness ranges from 42 to 48 cm for the three-headed walls, whereas is about 30 cm for the two-headed ones. At the intersection of perpendicular walls, the bricks are laid in a finger-jointed pattern, ensuring satisfactory bonding, Fig. 2.1.

Endoscopic surveys were carried out on one perimeter and one internal wall, Fig. 2.2. The tests confirmed the morphology and type of masonry; no internal cavities, voids, or anomalies were found. The data obtained were recorded in the form of videos and images on the instrument; the stratigraphy of the walls was reconstructed and reproduced in figures, see Report 3.1 for more details.

Fig. 2.1 Characterisation of masonry texture.

Fig. 2.2 Endoscopic surveys.

2.2.2 Penetrometric test on masonry

The purpose of the test is to assess the homogeneity of the various areas investigated and estimate the compressive strength of the mortar. It is a technique for evaluating the mechanical properties of mortar by driving a standardised metal probe into the material and measuring its penetration. The equipment consists of a calibrated gun that fires special metal nozzles with a predetermined load. It is an "indentation" method and the parameter measured is the depth of the cavity left by the probe on the surface being tested.

A total of 10 penetrometric tests were carried out, see Fig. 2.3. The single measurement obtained is the average value of 3 hits. The measurements taken were then correlated with the compressive strength of the material using the appropriate correlation plots.

Fig. 2.3. Location of investigations: penetrometric tests.

Table 2.1 shows the compressive strength values at each measurement point. The values obtained range from 0.5 to 1.5 MPa, which identify a mortar with poor mechanical properties.

Table 2.1 Compressive strength of mortar from penetrometric test

Label	Average penetration [mm]	Compressive strength [MPa]
Pm.1	13.3	1.26
Pm.2	14.7	1.09
Pm.3	11.7	1.48
Pm.4	20.3	0.50
Pm.5	14.7	1.09
Pm.6	13.3	1.26
Pm.7	23.0	N.D.
Pm.8	13.7	1.21
Pm.9	15.7	0.98
Pm.10	20.0	0.53

2.2.3 Sonic tests

The ultrasonic survey consists of measuring the time that an electro-acoustic pulse takes to travel the distance through the medium to be tested, which is considered homogeneous and isotropic. Once the signal transit time has been measured and the distance between two transducers noted, it is possible to calculate the pulse velocity, v . The pulse velocity depends on the mechanical characteristics of the material and, in particular, on the elastic constants (Young's modulus, E ; Poisson's ratio, ν) and the density of the material, ρ .

Fig. 2.4. Location of investigations: sonic tests.

The investigations were carried out in the four areas of masonry indicated on the plan in Fig. 2.4. All the masonry walls investigated are made of bricks laid in regular courses. For each area, a series of measurements were taken of the time required for the mechanical wave generated by the impact of the instrumented hammer on the opposite side of the masonry to travel through the wall. The measurements were taken on a 3x5 grid in a wall area measuring 75x125 cm. The elastic modulus is obtained from the wave velocity using the following equation

$$E = \frac{(1+\nu) \cdot (1-2\nu)}{(1-\nu)} \cdot \rho \cdot V^2. \quad (2.1)$$

Assuming a mass density $\rho = 1800 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and a Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.30$, the elastic modulus of the masonry, calculated using Eq. 2.1, is reported in Table 2.2. The values are comparable to those indicated by the Standard, approximately 1200÷1800 MPa for solid brick masonry. Among the factors that influence the measurements is the age of the conglomerate: the speed of wave propagation is inversely proportional to the curing age, and this is attributable to the micro-cracks that occur (speed reduction). High values of the elastic modulus indicate the absence of micro-cracks developed over time.

Table 2.2 Average velocity and Young's modulus of masonry from sonic test.

Label	Average velocity [m/s]	Young's modulus [MPa]
Son.1	1001	1366
Son.2	1417	2738
Son.3	1146	1791
Son.4	1375	2577

2.2.4 Tests with single flat jack

The use of single flat jacks in the diagnostics of masonry conditions aims to obtain the actual stress in a specific cross-section of the pier. The determination of the stress in the masonry is based on the variation of the deformation in a point of the structure due to a cut made in the

normal direction to the surface. During the execution of the cut, carried out using a special circular saw machine, the tension in the part above is released. The relaxation is detected using 2 or 3 measuring bases that register the elongation as the cut is completed. A flat jack is then inserted and pressurised. As the pressure increases, the transducers detect the recovery of the stress in the unperturbed configuration. The compressive stress of the wall is obtained from the following formula:

$$\sigma_v = P \cdot \frac{A_m}{A_t} \cdot k_m, \quad (2.2)$$

where:

σ_v = vertical working stress on the cross section of the wall (MPa);

P = pressure value to restore conditions prior to cutting (MPa) in the flat jack;

A_m = 778.56 cm² jack area;

A_t = 865 cm² cut area;

K_m = 0.86 jack edge constant.

Two tests were conducted which have involved an external transverse wall (test Mps.1) and an external longitudinal one (test Mps.2), see Fig. 2.5.

Fig. 2.5. Location of investigations: single and double jacks.

In the first case, see Table 2.3 and Fig. 2.8, there is a recovery to the initial deformation conditions when a pressure of 0.55 MPa is applied through the jack, which corresponds to a vertical stress σ_0 of 0.426 MPa in the wall. In the second case, see Table 2.4 and Fig. 2.9, there is a recovery to the initial deformation conditions when a pressure in the range 0.70÷0.80 MPa is applied, which corresponds to a vertical stress σ_0 of 0.542÷0.619 MPa.

The investigations tend to overestimate the vertical compressive stresses in the walls compared to the values obtained from numerical models.

Table 2.3 and Fig. 2.6. Vertical stress vs displacements in flat jack test Mps. 1

P	S1	S2	S3	σ_v
[MPa]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[MPa]
0.00	0.013	0.026	0.015	0.000
0.10	0.011	0.023	0.013	0.077
0.20	0.009	0.009	0.011	0.155
0.25	0.008	0.009	0.01	0.194
0.30	0.007	0.008	0.009	0.232
0.35	0.007	0.006	0.009	0.271
0.40	0.006	0.004	0.008	0.310
0.45	0.005	0.003	0.006	0.348
0.50	0.004	0.002	0.006	0.387
0.55	0.002	0.000	0.005	0.426

Table 2.4 and Fig. 2.7. Vertical stress vs displacements in flat jack test Mps. 2

P	S1	S2	σ_v
[MPa]	[mm]	[mm]	[MPa]
0.00	0.15	0.09	0.000
0.10	0.17	0.07	0.077
0.20	0.10	0.07	0.155
0.30	0.08	0.05	0.232
0.40	0.07	0.04	0.310
0.50	0.05	0.03	0.387
0.60	0.03	0.01	0.464
0.70	0.02	0.00	0.542
0.80	0.00	-0.02	0.619

2.2.5 Test with double flat jacks

The use of double flat jacks is aimed at determining the mechanical characteristics of the masonry (Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, compressive strength) on site. Once the service load of the masonry wall has been determined, a second jack is installed parallel to the first at a distance of approximately 30÷40 cm. An additional transducer with a measurement base of 35 cm is installed between the two jacks. The volume of material between the two jacks is subjected to a compression test by simultaneously increasing the pressure on the jacks. The pressure is increased until failure, which is identified by following the stress-strain curve and by visual inspection of the masonry.

Two tests were conducted which have involved an external longitudinal wall (test Mpd.1) and an internal one (test Mpd.2), see Fig. 2.5.

Two tests were carried out on the first floor of the building. The experimental values of Young's modulus and compressive strength were compared with the data reported in the scientific literature and in Circular 2019 for masonry walls of the same type.

Given the experimental constitutive stress-strain law, at each stress step i , Young's modulus is calculated as

$$E(i) = \frac{\sigma(i) - \sigma(i-1)}{\varepsilon(i) - \varepsilon(i-1)}, \quad (2.3)$$

and the tangential modulus of elasticity as

$$G(i) = \frac{E(i)}{2(1+\nu(i))}, \quad (2.4)$$

with $\nu(i) = -\varepsilon_{\text{transv}}(i) / \varepsilon(i)$ Poisson's ratio at i -th step.

- **MPd.1 test**

The stress-strain diagram obtained from test MPd.1 is shown below in Fig. 2.8. In addition to the strains at the four measurement points (three vertical, $\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3$; one horizontal, ε_4) for each pressure increment, Table 2.5 shows the values of the normal and tangential elasticity moduli calculated from the strain ε_2 at the central point.

The double jack test yielded values for compressive strength of the masonry of 2.01 MPa, for average Young's modulus of 2303 MPa, for average tangential modulus of 1118 MPa.

Fig. 2.8. Constitutive stress-strain law for test MPd.1.

Table 2.5. Evaluation of longitudinal and transversal moduli of elasticity for test MPd.1. The compression strength is highlighted with blue fill.

σ [MPa]	ϵ_1 [‰]	ϵ_2 [‰]	ϵ_3 [‰]	ϵ_4 [‰]	E [MPa]	G [MPa]
0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000		
0.155	0.024	0.051	0.007	-0.009		
0.310	0.034	0.176	0.088	-0.009	1234	588
0.464	0.034	0.241	0.132	-0.009	2404	1160
0.619	0.072	0.308	0.142	-0.009	2283	1110
0.774	0.121	0.373	0.146	-0.009	2404	1174
0.929	0.141	0.424	0.149	-0.009	3045	1492
1.084	0.166	0.478	0.156	-0.009	2854	1402
1.238	0.183	0.532	0.302	-0.014	2854	1389
1.393	0.231	0.647	0.325	-0.046	1343	627
1.548	0.303	0.817	0.481	-0.171		
1.703	0.414	1.092	0.597	-0.272		
1.858	0.524	1.420	0.902	-0.446		
2.013	0.686	1.905	1.485	-0.745		
2.013	1.028	2.210	1.990			
0.929	-0.059	1.729	-0.058			
average values					2303	1118

- **MPd.2 test**

The stress-strain diagram obtained from test MPd.2 is shown in Fig. 2.9. In addition to the strains at the four measurement points for each pressure increment, Table 2.6 shows the values of the normal and tangential elasticity moduli calculated from the strain ϵ_2 at the central point.

The double jack test yielded values for compressive strength of the masonry of 2.01 MPa, for average Young's modulus of 1364 MPa, for average tangential modulus of 477 MPa.

Fig. 2.9. Constitutive stress-strain law for test MPd.2.

Table 2.6. Evaluation of longitudinal and transversal moduli of elasticity for test MPd.2. The compression strength is highlighted with blue fill.

σ_v [MPa]	ϵ_1 [‰]	ϵ_2 [‰]	ϵ_3 [‰]	ϵ_4 [‰]	E [MPa]	G [MPa]
0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000		
0.155	0.362	0.647	0.179	-0.432		
0.310	0.524	0.816	0.263	-0.432		
0.464	0.627	0.953	0.332	-0.439	1131	387
0.619	0.695	1.066	0.389	-0.445	1368	483
0.774	0.773	1.158	0.445	-0.495	1681	589
0.929	0.854	1.255	0.500	-0.534	1590	558
1.084	0.954	1.403	0.589	-0.595	1051	369
1.238	1.178	1.703	0.739	-0.758		
1.393	1.349	1.979	0.911	-0.932		
1.548	1.657	2.461	1.139	-1.145		
1.703	2.105	3.276	1.529	-1.803		
1.858	2.508	4.324	1.979	-2.374		
2.013	3.392	5.353	2.384	-0.595		
2.167	4.643	7.926	3.347	-6.055		
2.167	5.103	9.179	3.758	-7.747		
1.084	4.884	8.811	3.379	-7.811		
average values					1364	477

2.2.6 *Shear strength tests on mortar joints (shove tests)*

The test consists of applying a horizontal force to a masonry block using a hydraulic jack in order to obtain the shear strength; once the compressive stress has been determined, the shear strength in the absence of axial stress f_{v0} can be calculated. To perform the test, it is necessary to create a housing in the masonry on one side of the block being tested, that is large enough to insert a hydraulic actuator and, on the other side, a housing with a height equal to that of the block and a width of approximately 10 mm, such as to allow the block to slide without interacting with the adjacent one, Fig. 2.10.

During the test, both the pressure applied to the hydraulic jack and the horizontal displacement of the test element are recorded using a displacement transducer. The test is performed by gradually increasing the pressure until the horizontal displacement of the brick occurs: this value corresponds to a force from which it is possible to obtain the shear strength of the mortar joint at a given level of vertical stress.

Tests were performed in the apartment on the first floor; their location on plan view is shown in Fig. 2.11.

Fig. 2.10. Diagram of the test equipment inserted into the masonry.

Fig. 2.11. Location of the investigations: shove tests.

The shear strength value in the absence of axial stress in masonry f_{v0} can be estimated by substituting expression (2.6) into expression (2.5) below:

$$F_v = 2 f_v A_1 + f_{v0} A_2 \quad (2.5)$$

$$f_v = f_{v0} + \mu \sigma_0 \quad (2.6)$$

where:

- F_v : maximum force reached during the test;
- A_1 : horizontal sliding surface, see Fig. 2.12;
- A_2 : vertical sliding surface, see Fig. 2.12;
- f_v : shear strength of masonry in the presence of compressive stress;
- f_{v0} : shear strength of masonry under zero compressive stress;
- σ_0 : vertical normal stress estimated on the mid-plane of the specimen;
- μ : internal friction coefficient of masonry (conservatively assumed to be 0.8).

Fig. 2.12. Horizontal and vertical sliding surfaces in Eq. (2.5).

Since, according to experiments reported in scientific/technical literature, the internal friction coefficient assumes average values close to 0.6-0.7 and can even reach values of 0.8, a value of 0.8 is conservatively assumed when calculating shear resistance in the absence of axial action. Therefore, substituting (2.6) into (2.5) yields:

$$f_{v0} = (F_v - 1.6 \sigma_0 A_1) / (2 A_1 + A_2). \quad (2.7)$$

Since the experimental shear resistance from the shove test is rather sensitive to variations in normal stress acting on the lower and upper surfaces of the brick, a finite element model of the building was first developed to accurately describe its geometry, stiffness of the resistant elements, stress distribution, under service conditions. The numerical model (Fig. 2.13) was developed using MIDAS FEA NX software (version 1.1, 2025), based on the drawings and geometric survey. The masonry walls were modelled with three or four nodes shell elements placed at the vertices, with six degrees of freedom for each node. In order to approximate the openings and to take into account the stiffening contribution of piers and spandrels with satisfactory accuracy, a rather dense discretisation was used; the dimensions of the elements

are generally less than 0.35x0.35 m. Ideal joint restraints were applied at the base of the building. The self-weight of the walls is automatically calculated by the software, given the weight per unit volume of the materials; the dead loads and live loads were entered at each floor in proportion to the area of influence. A linear static analysis was carried out to determine the normal stresses in horizontal and vertical (Fig. 2.14) directions.

In a second phase, local analyses were performed to estimate the increase in vertical stresses produced by the removal of a brick from the masonry during the experimental investigations. The wall involved in the sliding test was modelled with solid elements (edge dimensions between 0.025 and 0.050 m) to assess the increase of vertical stress in the brick due to the creation of a seat for the insertion of the actuator on one side, and to allow horizontal movement on the other.

Fig. 2.13. Numerical model with shell elements of the building.

Fig. 2.14. Contour plot of normal stress in vertical direction.

- **Test ST.1**

The load-displacement plot for test ST1 is shown in Fig. 2.15..

Fig. 2.15. Load-displacement diagram of sample ST.1.

The finite element model for the isolated wall is shown in Fig. 2.16. The wall is fixed at the base (pinned constraints), while a vertical pressure acts on the upper transversal cross-section, calculated from the global numerical model described in the previous section, at a distance sufficiently far from the discontinuity produced by the test.

The vertical stress σ_0 is obtained as the average of the values acting on the horizontal mid-plane of the brick. Two configurations were considered. In the first, the wall is undisturbed (reference configuration, Fig. 2.17), while in the second, two seats adjacent to the brick were created (test configuration, Fig. 2.18). In the former case, the average compressive stress in the brick is 0.280 MPa; in the latter case, it reaches 0.445 MPa, with a percentage increase of approximately 60%.

Fig. 2.16. The finite element model of the wall fixed at the bottom base and pressure loads applied on the top base.

Fig. 2.17. Contour plot of normal stress in vertical direction in the reference configuration.

Fig. 2.18. Contour plot of normal stress in vertical direction in the test configuration.

Assessment of shear strength of masonry under zero compressive stress

Brick dimensions:

$b \times s \times h = 260 \times 120 \times 60 \text{ mm}$;

Horizontal sliding surface:

$A_1 = b \times s = 31200 \text{ mm}^2$;

Vertical sliding surface:

$A_2 = b \times h = 15600 \text{ mm}^2$;

Average compressive stress on the mid-plane of the brick:

$\sigma_0 = 0.445 \text{ MPa}$;

Maximum load detected during the test:

$F_v = 33900 \text{ N}$;

Shear strength under zero compressive stress:

$f_{v0} = 0.150 \text{ MPa}$.

- **Test ST.2**

The load-displacement plot for test ST.2 is shown in Fig. 2.19.

Fig. 2.19. Load-displacement diagram of sample ST.2.

The finite element model for the isolated wall is shown in Fig. 2.20. The wall is fixed at the base (pinned constraints), while a vertical pressure acts on the upper transversal cross-section, calculated from the model described in the previous section, at a distance sufficiently far from the discontinuity produced by the test.

Fig. 2.20. The finite element model of the wall fixed at the bottom base and pressure loads applied on the top base.

The vertical stress σ_0 is obtained as the average of the values acting on the horizontal mid-plane of the brick. Two configurations were considered. In the first, the wall is undisturbed

(reference configuration, Fig. 2.21), while in the second, two seats adjacent to the brick were created (test configuration, Fig. 2.22). In the former case, the average compressive stress in the brick is 0.267 MPa; in the latter case, it reaches 0.350 MPa, with a percentage increase of approximately 30%.

Fig. 2.21. Contour plot of normal stress in vertical direction in the reference configuration.

Fig. 2.22. Contour plot of normal stress in vertical direction in the test configuration.

Assessment of shear strength of masonry under zero compressive stress

Brick dimensions:	$b \times s \times h = 195 \times 120 \times 60 \text{ mm};$
Horizontal sliding surface:	$A_1 = b \times s = 23400 \text{ mm}^2;$
Vertical sliding surface:	$A_2 = b \times h = 11700 \text{ mm}^2;$
Average compressive stress on the mid-plane of the brick:	$\sigma_0 = 0.350 \text{ MPa};$
Maximum load detected during the test:	$F_v = 17490 \text{ N}$
Shear strength under zero compressive stress:	$f_{v0} = 0.075 \text{ MPa}.$

2.2.6.1 Test ST.3

The load-displacement plot for test ST.3 is shown in Fig. 2.23. The test cannot be considered reliable, as the brick tended to rotate around a vertical axis rather than slide due to a protrusion in the adjacent seat.

Fig. 2.23. Load-displacement diagram of sample ST.3.

From the ST1 and ST2 shove tests, the mean value of strength due to the "ladder" cracking is equal to:

$$f_{v0} = (0.150 + 0.075) / 2 = 0.113 \text{ MPa}.$$

Now, it is necessary to calculate a shear strength value for diagonal tensile cracking, to be included in the definition of the plastic hinges implemented in the finite element software used to assess the seismic vulnerability of the building. This involves finding an equivalent τ_0 strength, i.e. such that it provides the same shear resistance of the wall, in the range of compressive stresses in service conditions. Thus, from the comparison between the strengths associated to the two failure mechanisms, it has assumed

$$\tau_0 = 0.40 f_{v0} = 0.045 \text{ MPa},$$

which is also in good agreement with the range of values suggested in Table C8.5.I of Circular 2019 for a similar masonry type.

2.2.7 Pull-out tests, sclerometric and ultrasonic surveys

The pull-out test consists of measuring the force required to extract a metal post-inserted in a concrete element. The extraction force is correlated to the compressive strength of material. A total of three pull-out tests were carried out on the reinforced concrete beam supporting the balcony on the front façade of the building.

The compressive strength of the concrete in situ was assessed by correlating the measurements obtained from the sclerometer and ultrasonic surveys. The survey focused on the reinforced concrete beam supporting the balcony.

By cross-referencing the results of the pull-out, sclerometric and sonic tests, the average compressive strength of the concrete, R_{cm} , in the beams can be estimated to be in the range of 27÷32 MPa. From the sonic tests, Young's modulus can be assumed to be 30,000 MPa.

2.2.8 Reinforcement surveys with pacometer

The reinforcement was investigated using non-destructive testing methods with a pacometer. The beam supporting the balcony on the front façade of the building and the ring beams on the second floor were investigated.

Three smooth longitudinal reinforcements $\varnothing 10\div\varnothing 12$ were detected at the supports in the beam. An additional bar of the same diameter is present in the mid-span. The transverse reinforcement consists of $\varnothing 6\div\varnothing 8$ stirrups at 40 cm intervals. The concrete cover varies between 10 and 20 mm. There is no reinforcement in the ring beams at floor level.

2.2.9 Testing of floor slabs and joists.

In order to define the floor layering and assess the intensity of the dead loads, the results of the visual surveys were cross-referenced with partially destructive tests. In particular, the construction type, the reinforcement in the lower side, the thicknesses, the joist spacing, were measured. Two inspections were carried out on the first and second floor levels.

The intermediate floors are made of reinforced concrete ribs and hollow clay bricks (usually known of SAP-type), see Table 2.7. Reinforcement consists of 2 $\varnothing 3$ lateral and 1 $\varnothing 4$ central smooth bars in each rib.

Table 2.7. Stratigraphy of the floor in the living area.

Material	
1 - Tiled pavement	(24.0 kN/m ³ , thickness 1 cm)
2 - Sand and cement screed	(22.0 kN/m ³ , thickness 4 cm)
3 - Type SAP floor	(height h = 12+4 cm)
4 - Plaster	(20.0 kN/m ³ , thickness 1 cm)

2.2.10 *Visual inspections*

Below are some pictures from survey of the building, that illustrates materials and construction techniques used.

Above the partition wall (brick joist only). The partition wall is made of 8 cm hollow bricks. Total thickness 12 cm with plaster.

Above the partition wall, there appears to be only a ring beam in the centre, with mortar joints on the sides.

Above the partition wall, there appears to be only a ring beam in the centre, with mortar joints on the sides.

Intersection of partition wall and transversal perimeter wall.

Intersection of transversal and longitudinal perimeter walls (front of building).

Intersection of transversal and longitudinal perimeter walls (rear of building).

Intersection of apartment boundary wall and longitudinal perimeter wall (rear of building)

Texture of the transversal perimeter wall

Perimeter corner front-balcony

Intersection of floor slab and front perimeter wall. Joist width 20 cm, with 3 slots for reinforcement

Front wall lintel 15 cm thick, height 16 or 13 at the ends

Front perimeter window lintel (left end). Indentation 12 cm, height 15 (or 13 at the ends)

*Reinforcement: 2 Ø3 lateral and 1 Ø4 central smooth bars.
Triangular hole tiles*

Floor-transversal perimeter wall

Longitudinal perimeter wall texture (front)

Longitudinal perimeter wall beam ring (front)

Floor/perimeter curb recess (longitudinal front wall)

2.3 Description of any potential cracking and/or degradation scenario

Visual inspection revealed no observable signs of structural damage or material degradation: no structural cracks were identified, surfaces were intact, with no signs of flaking or delamination. No evidence of differential settlements, distortions, or misalignments were observed.

It should be noted, however, that the unreinforced concrete of the basement walls has low compressive strength due to the friability of the material, which consists of coarse-grained gravel, sand, and is weakly bound.

2.4 Technical drawings

ANNEX A of this report contains the structural drawings of the ATER building in its current condition, including the structural plans of all levels, the elevations views, and relevant sections for the two main directions. They serve as a reference point for assessing the present state and supporting the plan of strengthening intervention.

3 The building of ZVKDS in Ljubljana

A series of inspections and survey activities were conducted on-site to assess the existing conditions and gather relevant data for the ongoing project. The purpose of these investigations was to investigate structural components consistency and integrity, geometric conformity with original drawings, relevant architectural finishes.

To that, a combination of non-invasive and standard field investigation techniques was utilized:

- Visual inspections: comprehensive walk-through inspections were carried out to identify the building features and details, including visible defects, signs of degradation, cracking, deformation, and other anomalies;
- Geometric survey: a detailed geometric survey was performed. This included the mapping of site boundaries, elevation profiles, and the layout of existing structures;
- Photographic Documentation: all observations were supported by high-resolution photographic records to provide visual references for existing site conditions and identified issues.

The surveys findings have been herein collected and will be used to inform the next phase of design and/or remedial works.

3.1 Description of the structure (as-is status)

The building is located in Ljubljana, at Slovenska cesta 28 (Fig. 3.1) and was constructed in 1895 (the year of the Ljubljana earthquake). There are indications on archive photos that the building survived well that strong earthquake (M6,1, EMS VIII-IX).

It consists of a basement, a ground floor, two upper floors, and an inhabited attic. The building's footprint measures approximately 40 × 17 m, with a total height from ground level to the ridge of about 20 m. The clear story heights are 4.90 m at the ground floor, 3.74 m on the first floor, 3.45 m on the second floor, and 6.28 m in the attic.

Originally was attic empty (maintenance access only) but was renovated into apartment in year 2008 [1]. The lower floors are currently used for retail, while the upper floors are used for office and residential purposes. The building is protected as cultural heritage building (EŠD 18643 and EŠD 18652) so additional care must be taken when choosing strengthening techniques.

All walls are built with solid brick. The wall thicknesses are 75 cm in the basement and ground floor (facing street), 60 cm at the ground floor and upper floors, and 45 cm in the attic. Most of the perpendicular (to the street) walls are of 30 cm or 15 cm thickness. They are positioned above walls in lower floors all the way to the foundation. The walls are built in standard masonry bond patterns, with mortar joints fully filled.

The floor structures are of the “Prussian vault” type on all levels (shallow brick masonry vaults spanning between iron I-beams). In the ground floor the vaults are deeper than in the upper stories.

Fig. 3.1 Front façade of building.

3.2 Inspection of building structure and material testing

An inspection of the building structure and material testing was carried out by opening 11 inspection probes to assess the type and layout of masonry (Fig. 3.3-Fig. 3.5). The investigation revealed that the walls are composed of solid bricks (sizes of old Austrian format) bonded with a weak lime mortar, with an estimated compressive strength of approximately 0,5-1,0 MPa. Sample bricks were taken into laboratory and tested for compression strength (by SIST EN 722-1).

The clay bricks are of solid format (Fig. 3.2), with approximate dimensions of $29 \times 14 \times 7$ cm (with deviations up to 5 mm). The material tests determined an average compressive strength of the brick: 8.4 MPa (after applying the correction factor for the b/h ratio of the specimens), with a standard deviation of ± 3.9 MPa; these are (expectedly) low values for old brick. The specific weight of the tested brick is 1.59 kg/m^3 . These findings indicate that the masonry has low mechanical resistance, which is an important factor to consider in evaluating the structural capacity and planning any necessary strengthening or repair measures.

The mechanical properties of the masonry were determined based on the results of tested samples of bricks, mortar assessment and observed morphology of walls. From there, the mean values were taken from literature, corresponding to masonry types that had been tested experimentally on wall sized specimens (example of tests in chapter 7.2.1.2 in [2]). In particular, the properties reported in Table 3.1 were assumed.

Table 3.1 Masonry material characteristics

Mechanical parameter	Mean value
Compressive strength f_c	2.50 MPa
Tensile strength f_t	0.09 MPa
Specific weight	16 kN/m ³
Elastic modulus E_m	800 MPa
Shear modulus G_m	260 MPa

Fig. 3.2 Samples of bricks to be tested.

Below are some pictures from survey of the building, that illustrates materials and construction techniques used.

Fig. 3.3 Photographs from the survey to determine construction details and materials (masonry with solid clay bricks and old earthquake ties made of flat iron).

Fig. 3.4 Masonry of solid clay bricks – old Austrian format of dimensions (approx. 29 x 14 x 6.5 cm).

Fig. 3.5 Photographs from survey to determine construction details and materials.

Fig. 3.6 Photographs from survey: street façade openings / back side main arch opening.

Fig. 3.7 Photographs from survey: window and door niche.

Fig. 3.8 Photographs from survey: masonry vaults between steel girders (left: ground floor, right upper floors).

Fig. 3.9 Photographs from survey: masonry vaults (right: Probe through the crown of the brick vault to determine the thickness of the layers)

The intermediate floor structures are shallow brick vaults between riveted steel beams (Fig. 3.10). The beams are embedded at least 30 cm deep into the thicker load-bearing walls. The dimensions of the vaults vary depending on their span and position, as well as their importance in the floor plan – on the street-facing side they are shallower. The rise of the vault is about 40 cm for larger spans and about 30 cm for smaller ones. Probing revealed at the crown first a 14 cm thick brick vault, followed by backfill up to 15 cm, and above this a 9 cm screed (apparently added during later renovations). In total, approximately 40 cm.

The staircase (Fig. 3.11) has two flights of stairs with intermediate landings. It is built of stone steps built into the wall in a cantilevered manner.

Foundations under the building were not inspected but are considered in good shape as there are no visible cracks that would correspond to differential settlement of foundation or insufficient loadbearing capacity.

Fig. 3.10 Schematics of different barrel vaults

Fig. 3.11 Photographs from survey: stone staircase.

3.3 Description of any potential cracking and/or degradation scenario

Visual inspection revealed no observable signs of structural damage or material degradation: no structural cracks were identified, surfaces were intact, with no signs of flaking or delamination. No evidence of differential settlements, distortions, or misalignments were observed. Also, no rust stains, efflorescence, or water ingress were detected.

3.4 Technical drawings

ANNEX B of this report contains the structural drawings of the ZVKDS building in its current condition, including the structural plans of all levels, the elevations views, and relevant sections for the two main directions. They serve as a reference point for assessing the present state and supporting the plan onf strengthening intervention.

Acknowledgments

The PRO-SIS project is funded by the Interreg VI-A Italy-Slovenia Programme 2021-2027, co-funded by the European Union.

All the project partners that actively contributed to the project are gratefully acknowledged.

References

- [1] Gattesco N. et al., 2025. Report 3.1 "Collection of drawings of selected buildings and description of characteristics". PRO-SIS report.
- [2] PERPETUATE, FP7 grant 244229, Deliverable 15: Results of laboratory and in-situ tests on masonry properties and tables with mechanical parameters to be adopted in numerical modelling, 2012.

FLOOR -1
Scale 1:50

1st FLOOR
Scale 1:50

DETAIL J
Scale 1:10

SECTION 1-1
Scale 1:100

SECTION 2-2
Scale 1:50

SECTION 3-3
Scale 1:50

BACK FAÇADE
Scale 1:50

SIDE FAÇADE
Scale 1:50

FRONT FAÇADE
Scale 1:50

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PRO-SIS Report 3.2 - ANNEX B_Structural drawings of the ZVKDS building in Ljubljana – unstrengthened status

 vault
 old brick masonry

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ZVKDS building, Slovenska 28, Ljubljana
Basement, unstrengthened

Scale
1:100

Sheet n°
3.2-B1

PRO-SIS Report 3.2 - ANNEX B_Structural drawings of the ZVKDS building in Ljubljana – unstrengthened status

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ZVKDS building, Slovenska 28, Ljubljana	Scale	Sheet n°
Ground floor, unstrengthened	1:100	3.2-B2

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PRO-SIS Report 3.2 - ANNEX B_Structural drawings of the ZVKDS building in Ljubljana – unstrengthened status

PRO-SIS Report 3.2 - ANNEX B_Structural drawings of the ZVKDS building in Ljubljana – unstrengthened status

 vault
 old brick masonry

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ZVKDS building, Slovenska 28, Ljubljana

Attic, unstrengthened

Scale
1:100

Sheet n°
3.2-B5

Longitudinal cross section A-A

Longitudinal cross section B-B

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ZVKDS building, Slovenska 28, Ljubljana

Cross sections, unstrengthened

Scale
1:100

Sheet n°
3.2-B7

Longitudinal cross section C-C

PRO-SIS Report 3.2 - ANNEX B_Structural drawings of the ZVKDS building in Ljubljana – unstrengthened status

Transversal cross section A'-A'

Transversal cross section B'-B'

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ZVKDS building, Slovenska 28, Ljubljana

Cross sections, unstrengthened

Scale

1:100

Sheet n°

3.2-B9

PRO-SIS Report 3.2 - ANNEX B_Structural drawings of the ZVKDS building in Ljubljana – unstrengthened status

Transversal cross section A'-A'

Transversal cross section B'-B'

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ZVKDS building, Slovenska 28, Ljubljana
Cross sections, unstrengthened

Scale
1:100

Sheet n°
3.2-B9

Front view

ZVKDS building, Slovenska 28, Ljubljana
Facades unstrengthened

Scale
1:100
Sheet n°
3.2-B11

PRO-SIS Report 3.2 - ANNEX B_Structural drawings of the ZVKDS building in Ljubljana – as is status

Rear view

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ZVKDS building, Slovenska 28, Ljubljana

Facades, unstrengthened

Scale

1:100

Sheet n°

3.2-B12